

An open-source tool to assess shadow flicker of wind turbines: The WIMBY_SF tool

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Abstract

Wind power is critical for the energy transition, yet its expansion faces local resistance due to concerns such as visual impact, noise, and shadow flicker (SF). SF, caused by rotating turbine blades, has been associated with social and environmental impacts. Existing SF assessment tools are either simplistic or proprietary, limiting accessibility. This paper presents the **WIMBY_SF tool**, an open-source Python-based solution for SF simulation integrating python based geo-libraries, advanced shadow geometry transformation over complex terrain, and approximated turbine operation. It refines visibility constraints through viewshed analysis and accurately accounts for topographic influences. WIMBY_SF tool was validated against WindPRO using hypothetical turbine locations in Spain including areas with complex terrain. The SF-affected areas above 30 hours/year show strong agreement with WindPRO, with Pearson's correlation coefficient of 0.907 (p -value < 0.01), demonstrating WIMBY_SF tool's accuracy compared to the industrial standard. The WIMBY_SF tool, being open-source, enhances transparency and accessibility in SF assessments, supporting policymakers, developers, and the public for decision-making in wind power deployment.

1. Introduction

Wind power is one of the most mature, cost-effective source of low-carbon electricity and a key technology for the energy transition. Its contribution to the energy matrix of several countries is expected to grow in the coming decades. However, this growth faces multiple challenges, specifically the local resistance due to concerns about impacts on the landscape, the environment, local economy and human health (McKenna et al., 2025). Shadow flicker (SF), the intermittent effect caused when the rotating blades of a wind turbine cast shadows over nearby areas, is a recurrent topic associated to human health impacts.

The SF frequency that could be achieved by modern wind turbines is in a range that would not directly affect the health of people (not even the most vulnerable ones i.e. people with photosensitive epilepsy), but there is a body of literature reporting on people feeling annoyed by it (Pawlaczyk-Łuszczynska et al., 2014; Michaud et al., 2016a, 2016b; Brinckerhoff, 2011; Pohl, Gabriel, & Hübner, 2018). While SF is often discussed alongside more prominent concerns like noise or visual disturbance, recent literature reviews such as Teneler and Hassoy (2023); Freiberg et al. (2019) gathered studies showing that annoyance caused by SF can affect a subset of the population, particularly in rural settings and close proximity to turbines. Freiberg et al. (2019) found that the pooled prevalence of high annoyance due to shadow flicker was 6%, with substantial heterogeneity; when focusing on studies conducted in rural areas with

a high number of wind turbines, the pooled prevalence increased to 9%.

SF alone explains only a small portion of the annoyance, but its influence grows in interaction with factors such as turbine audibility, perceived risk, and individual sensitivity (Voicescu et al., 2016). This annoyance can generate stress that could sometimes lead to health issues (Jeffery, Krogh, & Horner, 2013; Pawlaczyk-Łuszczynska et al., 2014). However, the reported annoyance due to SF among residents near wind turbines may not necessarily correlate with the actual physical exposure to SF at their location (Haac, Darlow, Kaliski, Rand, & Hoen, 2022). Therefore, we argue that having transparent and easy access to information about the actual SF impact of wind turbines could help to objectively assess and understand the reasons behind the annoyance of locals.

Multiple countries have regulations and guidelines about tolerance levels (in hours/year) for SF, which must be considered in planning and permission processes. The SF impact assessments (Voicescu et al., 2016; Peri & Tal, 2021; Haac et al., 2022; Zaporozhets, Levchenko, Glyva, & Burdeina, 2022) are either performed using simplified methods like applying buffer zones around individual turbines following rules of thumb, which tend to be inaccurate, or building statistical models, or using specialized software such as WindPRO (EMD-International, 2025), a proprietary tool, which has been identified as a standard for industry and academia. Such assessments are generally only accessible to experts and are

often only available to the public in lengthy documents involved in the permission request process of individual wind farms. This makes it difficult for home owners arriving to areas that already have wind farms and for citizen organizations seeking information on new projects to access such information. In an effort to make information about such impacts available to a wider public, the project WIMBY (Wind in My Backyard: Using holistic modelling tools to advance social awareness and engagement on large wind power installations in the EU) aims at creating an online and open interactive map for high-level planing of wind farms. One of the requirements to this map is the development of an open-source tool that allows for an accurate and fast assessment of the SF-impacted areas around individual wind turbines.

Reviewing the existing literature, we observed that no open-source existing tool could directly perform SF analysis. However, we found and tested several shadow-calculation packages, excluding GIS tools such as QGIS and GRASSGIS due to computational overhead. We examined descriptions, scientific publications, and source codes for tools such as pybdshadow (Yu & Li, 2024), pyny3d (Fernández-Fernández, 2024), Shadowtime (Osterberg, 2024), and the R library shadow (Dorman, Appelhans, Detsch, Wöllauer, & Nauss, 2019). Tools lacking support, requiring full 3D environments, or producing incompatible outputs were discarded. Among them, only the R shadow package (shadow-R), originally designed for urban shadow analysis, showed potential for adaptation with open-source R tools. However, shadow-R does not account for topographic effects, and requires multiple adaptations to properly model the yearly cumulative shadow effects of rotating wind turbines, which differ considerably from the static and ground-connected buildings represented in shadow-R. To address these limitations, we developed an open-source Python-based tool, WIMBY_SF tool, that accurately models turbine shadow projections over complex terrains and accounts for wind turbine operation hours depending on wind speeds derived from reanalysis data. Effort was made to keep the computational requirements to a minimum, and an iterative process was in place to improve the visualization of results.

2. Methodology

The WIMBY_SF tool is developed to model SF from individual wind turbines in a wind farm at any location in Europe. The calculation algorithm of the tool follows the following four consecutive steps:

1. Calculate shadow geometry;
2. Transform the geometry on Topography;
3. Include the wind condition to reflect operation patterns;
4. Compute the shadow footprint for specific moments for a given range of time based on 3;
5. Create a raster map with frequency of exposure to SF.

2.1. Shadow Geometry Calculation

The WIMBY_SF tool geometry calculation includes two sub-processes: (a) Determining the shadow length and position(section 2.1.1), and (b) Incorporating umbra and penumbra effects in elliptical Shadow Transformation (section 2.1.2).

2.1.1. Shadow Length and Position

The length of the turbine shadow is determined by the trigonometric projection of the turbine height and the solar elevation angle. Given a turbine of height h and a solar elevation ϵ_s , the shadow length L is given by:

$$L = h \cdot \tan(90^\circ - \epsilon_s) \quad (1)$$

where:

- h is the turbine height (m),
- ϵ_s is the solar elevation angle (degrees above the horizon).

If the computed shadow length exceeds the predefined maximum threshold L_{\max} the model constrains it to L_{\max} for that time step:

$$L = \begin{cases} L_{\max}, & \text{if } L > L_{\max} \\ L, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The shadow extends in the direction opposite to the solar azimuth, requiring a translation from the turbine location (X_O, Y_O) by a distance L along the shadow direction θ :

$$\theta = \alpha_s + 180^\circ \quad (3)$$

$$(x', y') = (X_O - L \cos \theta, Y_O - L \sin \theta) \quad (4)$$

where:

- α_s is the solar azimuth angle,
- (X_O, Y_O) represents the turbine location,
- (x', y') represents the shadow's translated centroid.

2.1.2. Umbra and Penumbra Considerations in Elliptical Shadow Transformation

When a wind turbine rotor obstructs sunlight, the resulting shadow consists of two distinct regions (Salazar Trujillo, 2014):

- **Umbra:** The fully shaded region where the Sun is completely blocked.
- **Penumbra:** A partially shaded transition zone where only part of the solar disk is obscured. (Figure 1)

An approximation to penumbra width can be calculated by the sun's angular diameter ($\alpha_{\text{sun}} \approx 0.53^\circ$). The penumbra width in Figure 1, denoted by W_p is:

$$W_p = D + 2L \tan(\alpha_{\text{sun}}) \quad (5)$$

where:

- D is the turbine rotor diameter (m),
- L is the shadow length (m),
- α_{sun} is the apparent solar angular diameter (radians).

The penumbra extends beyond the rotor's full shaded area Umbra, introducing a gradual light transition at the shadow edges (Salazar Trujillo, 2014) (Figure 1). This accounts for the fact that different parts of the Sun's disk are obscured at slightly different angles, causing the shadow to extend beyond a simple projection of the rotor. To incorporate this, WIMBY_SF tool models the shadow of the wind turbine rotor as an elliptical projection, dynamically adjusting its shape based on the rotor geometry and solar position.

Figure 1: Illustration of the shadow penumbra at the edge of a wind turbine's full shadow.

Source: Adapted from Salazar Trujillo (Salazar Trujillo, 2014).

The shadow elongates as the sun lowers in the sky, accurately reflecting the effects of changing solar elevation and azimuth. The semi-major axis S_x and semi-minor axis S_y of the shadow ellipse are given by:

$$S_x = \frac{L}{R} \quad (6)$$

$$S_y = \frac{W_p}{D} \quad (7)$$

where:

- R is the original rotor radius,
- W_p accounts for the penumbra expansion.

Each point (x', y') in the original circular rotor projection P is transformed into the scaled shadow ellipse as:

$$(x'', y'') = (x' \cdot S_x, y' \cdot S_y) \quad (8)$$

To correctly align the shadow with the sun's azimuth, the 2D rotation matrix is applied:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x''' \\ y''' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & -\sin \theta \\ \sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x'' \\ y'' \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Finally, the transformed shadow is translated to the correct shadow location:

$$(x_{\text{final}}, y_{\text{final}}) = (x''' + \Delta x, y''' + \Delta y) \quad (10)$$

where:

$$\Delta x = -L \cos \theta, \quad \Delta y = -L \sin \theta \quad (11)$$

Thus, the resulting shadow footprint is computed as:

$$S = \tau_{\Delta x, \Delta y} R_{\theta} S_{x, y}(P) \quad (12)$$

where:

- $\tau_{\Delta x, \Delta y}$ represents the translation,
- R_{θ} applies the rotation,
- $S_{x, y}$ applies the elliptical scaling.

2.2. Shadow Geometry Transformation on Topography

To accurately determine the shadowed area of a wind turbine over varied terrain, the turbine elevation is first retrieved from the Digital Surface Model (DSM). Using this elevation data and the DSM itself, three angular maps are generated:

- Altitude angle map for the turbine rotor top, α_{top} .
- Altitude angle map for the turbine rotor bottom, α_{bot} .
- Azimuth angle map toward the turbine, β .

Following the methodology in Nagy (1994), we compute these angular relationships as follows: For each pixel (i, j) in the DSM, the horizontal displacement from the turbine location (X_O, Y_O) is:

$$\Delta x = X_O - x_{ij}, \quad \Delta y = Y_O - y_{ij} \quad (13)$$

The horizontal distance is calculated as:

$$d_{ij} = \sqrt{\Delta x^2 + \Delta y^2} \quad (14)$$

The altitude angle α_{ij} and azimuth angle β_{ij} are then determined by:

$$\alpha_{ij} = \arctan 2(\Delta z, d_{ij}) \quad (15)$$

$$\beta_{ij} = \arctan 2(\Delta x, \Delta y) \quad (16)$$

where Δz represents the elevation difference between the turbine and pixel (i, j) . The altitude angle maps α_{top} and α_{bot} provide the vertical angles from each pixel to the turbine rotor (Figure 2 a) and b)), while β represents the horizontal direction from each pixel toward the turbine (Figure 2 c)).

Figure 2: (a) and (b) represent the altitude maps for one turbine, showing the vertical angles from each pixel to the turbine rotor top and bottom, respectively. (c) represents the azimuth map, which indicates the direction of each pixel relative to the turbine. (d) highlights the pixels that can be cast into shadow from the turbine rotor top, while (e) represents those cast from the turbine rotor bottom.

At each time step t , the solar angles are defined as:

- Solar altitude for rotor top: $A_{\text{top}}(t)$.
- Solar altitude for rotor bottom: $A_{\text{bot}}(t)$.
- Solar azimuth: $B(t)$.

Considering the Sun's angular diameter of approximately 0.53° , the corrected altitude thresholds are:

$$A_{\text{top-min}}(t) = A_{\text{top}}(t) - \frac{0.53}{2} \quad (17)$$

$$A_{\text{bot-max}}(t) = A_{\text{bot}}(t) + \frac{0.53}{2} \quad (18)$$

A pixel (i, j) is within the shadow altitude mask M_{alt} if:

$$\alpha_{\text{top}} \geq A_{\text{top-min}}(t), \quad \alpha_{\text{bot}} \leq A_{\text{bot-max}}(t) \quad (19)$$

which are shown in Figure 2 (d) and (e). Equivalently,

$$M_{\text{alt}} = (\alpha_{\text{top}} \geq A_{\text{top-min}}(t)) \wedge (\alpha_{\text{bot}} \leq A_{\text{bot-max}}(t)) \quad (20)$$

which is shown in Figure 3 (a). The azimuth mask M_{az} (Figure 3 (b)) is determined by comparing each pixel's azimuth angle β_{ij} with the Sun's azimuth $B(t)$, under a tolerance angle τ :

$$M_{\text{az}}(i, j) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } |(B(i, j) - B(t) + 360) \% 360| \leq \tau \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

The final shadow mask (Figure 3 (c)) is obtained by combining the altitude and azimuth masks:

$$M_{\text{shadow}}(i, j) = M_{\text{alt}}(i, j) \wedge M_{\text{az}}(i, j) \quad (22)$$

This mask defines the shadow footprint cast by the turbine rotor at each time step t .

Figure 3: (a) The altitude mask from Figure 2, computed as the difference between the altitude maps for the turbine rotor top and bottom. (b) The azimuth mask, incorporating a 5° tolerance. (c) The overlapping region of (a) and (b), effectively delineating the final shadow footprint at a given time step.

At this stage, the shadow area lacks the elliptical shadow transformation. To address this, the shadow length and shadow centroid derived from M_{shadow} are used to integrate the full shadow geometry projection on terrain. In the final step of the shadow transformation on topography, a visibility map is generated to identify topographical obstructions. This map uses the location of the turbine and the height (in the center of the turbine rotor) as the observer

position and calculates the viewshed from the turbine. The viewshed area represents regions where no obstacles obstruct the line of sight from the turbine. These areas can be directly reached by the turbine's shadow; thus, SF is expected. The goal is to generate this map and exclude the non-viewshed area from the previously computed transformed SF map.

To achieve this, we utilize the `gdal_viewshed` function, which calculates line-of-sight visibility from the observer position at:

$$(X_O, Y_O, h_O) \quad (23)$$

where:

- X_O, Y_O represent the turbine's coordinates,
- h_O is the observer height, computed as:

$$h_O = \text{turbine height} + \text{elevation} \quad (24)$$

Each pixel (X, Y) in the domain is considered visible from the observer if no point on the line segment between (X_O, Y_O) and (X, Y) exceeds the line-of-sight elevation. The visibility condition is given by:

$$\text{surface height}(X_i, Y_i) \leq h_O - (h_O - \text{surface height}(X, Y)) \times \frac{\text{distance}(X_O, Y_O, X_i, Y_i)}{\text{distance}(X_O, Y_O, X, Y)} \quad (25)$$

where (X_i, Y_i) is an intermediate point along the line-of-sight path. If at any sampled point this inequality does not hold, the line of sight is blocked, and (X, Y) is considered non-visible.

To optimize computation, a bounding box of ± 5 km from the turbine center is applied to clip the DSM, ensuring efficient processing for each turbine.

2.3. Including Wind Condition in the WIMBY_SF Tool

Since wind turbines operate within a specific wind speed range, defined by cut-in and cut-out thresholds, the WIMBY_SF tool can account for these conditions. When wind speeds fall below the cut-in threshold or exceed the cut-out threshold, the turbine remains stationary, eliminating SF. Not taking this into account means assuming continuous turbine operation, representing a worst-case scenario for SF calculations. In the WIMBY_SF users can decide between considering these operational thresholds or not.

To account for operational times we rely on wind speed data for the location of each simulated turbine. Wind speed data are sourced from the ERA5 (Hersbach et al., 2023). We use mean wind speed data for every hour in a day for each month (Hahmann, 2024b), which is bias corrected using data from the Global Wind Atlas V2 (Hahmann, 2024a). The derived ERA5 data set aggregates wind speed data from 2013–2022, covering Europe (35°N – 72°N , 15°W – 35°E) with a spatial resolution of $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$. The bias correction improves spatial resolution to $250\text{m} \times 250\text{m}$ for the hourly mean wind speeds at heights of 50 m, 100 m, and 200 m.

By default, the model applies a cut-in speed of 3 m/s and a cut-out speed of 25 m/s, with user-defined customisation available. For each time step and turbine location, the WIMBY_SF tool retrieves the corresponding hourly mean wind speed. If the wind

speed is outside the operational range, the turbine is assumed to be non-operational, and SF is not generated. This ensures that the WIMBY_SF tool provides a more realistic and dynamic assessment of SF exposure, aligning with actual wind turbine behavior.

2.4. Validation

To validate the SF projection model, we compared WIMBY_SF tool and WindPRO across 50 turbine locations in Spain, accounting for topographic influence. The turbines were selected at equal intervals along latitude 36.9–39.5 and longitude -3.563825 to span the longest land extent and intersect mountainous regions.

The worst-case scenario validation was conducted with a time resolution of 4-minute intervals per time step, a 14-day interval per day step, and a 30-meter map resolution across both tools.

For a robust quantitative validation, we based our validation on established regulatory thresholds. We only chose the SF areas where SF intensity was more than the threshold of 30 hours per year. Germany introduced a guideline for SF assessment in 2002, which influenced regulations in multiple countries (Länderausschuss für Immissionsschutz, 2002). The standard was revised in 2019 (Bund-/Länder-Arbeitsgemeinschaft für Immissionsschutz, 2020), setting a threshold of 30 hours per year and 30 minutes per day under the worst-case astronomical conditions. This threshold is widely used for SF impact assessment Koppen, Gunuru, and Chester (2017); Koppen and Ekelschot-Smink (2023).

To align with these regulatory benchmarks, we conducted a statistical analysis (Pearson correlation and error quantification) comparing the WIMBY_SF tool and WindPRO outputs for areas exceeding 30 hours of annual SF exposure. This approach ensures that the validation reflects real-world regulatory constraints and provides a meaningful comparison of model accuracy.

3. Result

3.1. Modeling Results

The WIMBY_SF tool (Chen & Ramirez Camargo, 2025) successfully integrates topographic influences into SF projections, and is ready to be applied as one of the impacts in WIMBY interactive map and the input for other WIMBY models. Figure 4 presents a SF map for a turbine located in Spain (37.5898, -3.5638). The units of the map are the intensity of SF exposure in hours/year, indicating the annual cumulative duration of SF. The black regions represent the non-visible areas excluded from SF calculations.

Further, the WIMBY_SF tool adapts to mountainous terrain, ensuring accurate SF representation. Figure 5 illustrates the SF distribution in a mountainous region of Spain, overlaid on the EU DSM resampled to 20 m resolution. The resampling was necessary to maintain the accuracy of the altitude angle maps (α_{top} and α_{bot}), ensuring precise calculations for SF projections. Using the original 30 m DSM resulted in distortions, particularly affecting the angle computations at higher solar altitudes, where the sun elevation approaches 90° around midday. These inaccuracies could lead to misrepresentations in the projected SF areas.

Figure 4: SF map (yellow to blue butterfly-shape area) excluding the view-blocked area (in black), for turbine location (43.2847, -7.6627) in Spain. Darker blue areas indicate greater SF exposure (hours/year).

Figure 5: SF distribution in a mountainous region in Spain for turbine location (37.5898, -3.5638), with the elevation map in background. Darker blue areas indicate greater SF intensity, with topography influencing shadow spread.

3.2. Validation Results

To validate the WIMBY_SF tool's accuracy, we compared its results with WindPRO across Spain with 50 turbines, representing mountainous terrain. The WIMBY_SF tool accounted for topographic variations and estimated a mean SF area of 808,686 m², closely matching WindPRO's 811,090 m². The Pearson's correlation coefficient was 0.907 (p-value < 0.01)(Figure 6 [a]), confirming strong agreement, with a root mean square deviation (RMSD) of 75,933 m². Discrepancies, as shown in Figure 6 [b], are primarily due to WIMBY_SF tool's higher-resolution viewshed analysis and enhanced shadow transformation methods. Despite a higher standard deviation in WIMBY_SF tool's results (161,780 m² vs. 111,439 m²), its estimates remain within WindPRO's range.

In general, the WIMBY_SF tool demonstrates high correlation (>0.907) and accurate treatment of topographic characteristics, making it a reliable open-source alternative to commercial software like WindPRO for SF modeling while maintaining accuracy across varied landscapes.

Figure 6: (a) Correlation between WIMBY_SF tool and WindPRO for Spain validation (Pearson's $r = 0.907$); (b) Relative error histogram showing minor deviations, mainly in complex terrains.

4. Discussion

The accuracy of the WIMBY_SF tool is highly dependent on the resolution of the input DSM. The current implementation requires a 20 m DSM resolution to generate precise altitude angle maps (α_{top} and α_{bot}), ensuring that shadow projection calculations remain accurate. Coarser resolutions (e.g., 30 m) introduce distortions in angle computations, particularly at high solar elevations, which can lead to inaccuracies in SF predictions. Future improvements could explore adaptive resolution techniques, dynamically adjust the level of DSM based on specific criteria, such as terrain complexity or the importance of certain regions in the analysis. Moreover, the current WIMBY_SF tool assumes a worst-case scenario, where the wind turbine rotor is modeled as a sphere, meaning it continuously faces the Sun regardless of wind direction. In reality, turbine rotors adjust dynamically based on wind direction, which affects the actual shadow cast. Implementing a wind-dependent rotor orientation

model would make the SF simulation more realistic by reducing the projected shadow area under certain conditions.

Beyond wind conditions, other meteorological parameters, such as cloud cover and atmospheric humidity, could significantly influence the occurrence and intensity of SF. Currently, the WIMBY_SF tool, compared to the full capabilities of WindPRO, does not account for cloudiness and other atmospheric effects, which can obscure sunlight and reduce SF intensity. Future work could integrate satellite-based cloud cover data to improve SF estimations. Similarly, variations in atmospheric humidity and aerosol concentration affect light scattering and diffusion, potentially modifying shadow characteristics. Incorporating these factors would further refine the model's ability to capture real-world SF impacts, improving its accuracy in diverse climatic regions.

5. Conclusions

We developed the WIMBY_SF tool, an open-source solution to accurately model SF from wind turbines over complex terrains. The validation of WIMBY_SF tool by comparing it to WindPRO demonstrated its accuracy. Using hypothetical turbines located in Spain, which included complex topographies, the WIMBY_SF tool maintained robustness across different landscapes, making it a reliable open-source alternative for worst-case scenario SF modeling.

As an open-access tool, the WIMBY_SF tool enhances the accessibility of SF impact assessments. Its integration into the WIMBY interactive map will enable transparent and user-friendly visualization of SF intensities, helping communities, policymakers, and developers in decision-making.

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